

Lecturers' Qualifications as a Predictor of Effective Teaching of Science Courses in Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria

Dr. Ahmad Kainuwa¹

Email: ahmadkainuwa@yahoo.com

Tel: 08032790239

Abdulaziz Bello¹

Email: abdulazizbello@yahoo.com

Tel: 08030776713

¹Department of Educational Foundations Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria

Abstract

This study investigated the extent to which lecturers' qualification could predict an effective teaching of science courses using faculty of science Federal University Gusau as a case study. The study adopted a descriptive case study research design of survey type to provide answers to the research questions using quantitative method in collecting the data. A total of 75 lecturers in the Faculty of Science formed the population of the study. Random sampling technique was used to take a total of 63 respondents from the said population. In analysing the data of this study, descriptive statistical analysis was undertaken using SPSS version 20; this involved frequencies, percentages and means. Inferential statistics was also conducted using multiple regressions to find out whether lecturer's qualification will serve as a predictor of effective teaching of science courses. The study found out statistically that, the lecturers' qualification serve as a predictor of effective teaching of science courses. The study recommended that, the University management should provide chances and opportunities for staff development and other in-service training programs to enhance and upgrade the lecture's levels of qualification. In a nutshell, The University Management should provide opportunities for training and development of lecturers.

Keywords: Effect, Lecturer's Qualifications, Predictor, Effective Teaching, Science Courses Federal University Gusau.

Introduction

Many lecturers in sub-Saharan Africa, including Nigeria, are not able to apply modern information technologies in teaching due to lack of qualification and computer illiteracy hence they mostly rely on lecture method of teaching (Eboutouet al., 1998; Haambokoma, 2002). Failure to expose learners to hands-on experiences has resulted in their low academic achievement in the Science, Mathematics and Technology (SMT) subjects namely Mathematics, Biology, Chemistry, Physics and Agriculture. A study by Adeogun (2001) in Nigeria found that the quality of any education system depends on the quality of teachers. Review of related literature indicates that the most important school-based determining factor of student's achievement is the teacher quality (Rivkin et al., 2005; Aaronson et al., 2007; Harris and Sass, 2008). Therefore, there is need to assess the characteristics of the lecturers in F U G

in terms of qualification, experience and teaching methodology in order to ensure quality of education given to the youths. The teachers of SMT should be in-serviced where gaps are identified to enable them to cope with the requirements of the dynamic school curriculum (Murunga et al., 2013). Ewer (2001) believes that science teaching plan is incomplete without science experience and available teaching aids that would simplify the teaching-learning effectively. Lack of qualified lecturers in teaching science courses is said to affects students' performance in the faculty of science at federal university Gusau.

In a study conducted by Aaronson (2007), different categories of teacher variables have been analyzed. Some studies focus on the impact of a teacher's gender and race on teacher quality (Dee, 2007) Tried to studied, the relationship between student outcomes and teacher qualifications such as teaching certificates or teaching experiences, Kane

(2008) Observed teacher characteristics are, however, generally found to have only little impact on student achievement and can only explain a relatively small part of overall teacher quality (Rivkin et al., 2005). Most of the variation in teacher quality can be attributed to unobserved factors. This finding led researchers, concerned with providing recommendations for recruitment policies and designing optimal teacher pay schemes, to suggest to identify effective teachers by their actual performance on the job using value added" measures of student achievement (Gordon et al., 2006).

Akisolu (2010) asserted that availability of qualify teachers determined the performance of student in schools. On the contrary, Igwe (1990) investigated the influence of teacher's qualification in Kano and reported that there is no significant relationship between teacher's qualification and student's performance. Huang and Moon (2009) states that teacher's qualification accounted for approximately 40 to 60 per cent of variance in the average of student's achievement in assessment.

In this study, Symbolic interactionism theory was used; this theory is more appropriate to be used in this study because, Symbolic interactionism approach or perspectives is concerned with ways in which teachers make sense and respond to the behavior of their students during teaching and learning activity in school as a micro-society. Description of symbolic interactionism as sociological perspective that cover all those approaches that investigate the social interactions among individual (student-student interaction and teacher-student interaction in their learning environment) rather than starting it from social structure under this auspices of this paradigm, engages with those social interactions and tries to learn about the basic foundations of the social context: the theory maintains that human interactions change constantly and undergo a process of structuring and restructuring that sociologist called the "social structuring of reality (Goffman 1959)

In light of the above theory it means that, learning by doing activity play a very vital role belongs to the group of didactic learning known as simulation activities and it takes place within the imagination. Role of the scientist in the understanding of any phenomena involves the practical activity in the group format of a student in a learning environment. Where actors (students) assume the roles of people in problematic social situations, presenting such situations help to clarify positions and interpersonal problems, as well as to identify alternative methods to solve the problems, generally, the "performance" is spontaneously presented, and the actors do not

compare or coordinate their roles upfront and do not rehearse a script or behaviour pattern in advance. The facilitator is present at the start of the story, and he/she is the person who has given the explanation and its background (Goffman 1959).

It is against this background that, this present research wants to carry out an investigation to see whether lecturers' qualification can serve as a predictor of effective teaching of science courses in federal University Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria with the aim of determining the appropriate teaching that would improve students' high academic achievements and ensure qualitative productions of manpower in the various fields of science courses, capable of making positive impacts in different sectors of development in Nigeria, after successful graduation from University.

Objectives of the Study

1. To investigate whether lecturers' qualifications can predict effective teaching of science courses in terms of presentation and pedagogy in Federal University Gusau.
2. To investigate whether lecturers' qualifications can predict effective teaching of science courses in terms of presentation and pedagogy in Federal University Gusau.

Research Questions

1. To what extents would the lecturers' qualifications predict effective teaching of science courses in terms of presentation and pedagogy in FUG?
2. To what extents would the lecturers' qualifications predict effective teaching of science courses in terms of classroom management and control in FUG?

Hypothesis

Lecturers' qualifications is not a predictor of effective teaching of science courses in Federal University Gusau.

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive case study research design of survey type to determine the degree of relationship between the independent variable (lecturer's qualification) and the dependent variable (effective teaching of science courses). The purpose of this study was to look into the extent to which lecturer's qualification can predict effective teaching of science courses in faculty of science Federal University Gusau. The findings in this paper are drawn from a research study on the official discourse versus pedagogic practice: a case study of science teaching at Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The specific research question that guided the study was: To investigate whether lecturers' qualifications can

predict effective teaching of science courses in FUG. To address this question, lecturer's qualification was categorized into graduate assistance to lecturer one (G A- L A) and senior lecturers to professors (SL-Professors).

In this study, the instrument used for data collection was "observation check list guide for teaching science courses in faculty of science" experts in sociology of education, measurement and evaluation, research methodology and English language were used in validating the instrument. The experts comprised of three professors and two PhD lecturers from Usman Danfodio University Sokoto. Their observations, instructions and comments ensured the content validity of the research instrument. The researchers performed reliability analysis to ensure that the measures of variables have internal consistency across the various items that measure the same concept or variable (Sekaran & Bougie, 2010).

Results

Research Question 1

To what extents would the lecturers' qualifications predict effective teaching of science courses in terms of presentation and pedagogy in FUG?

This section discusses the predicting influence of Lecturer's qualification on effective teaching of science courses in faculty of science in terms of Presentation and Pedagogy. To find out this predicting influence, a checklist observation of science teaching was used and conducted with the lecturers

The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach alpha yielding co-efficients of .74 respectively for all items. Data was collected from the science lecturers at Federal University Gusau, in their various lecture halls during the lectures. The total number of the lecturers stands at 75 out of which 63 science lecturers were used as sample size for this study. The choice of 63 science lecturers as sample, out of the estimated population is based on the table of Israel, (1992), Krejcie and Morgan, (1970).

The study used quantitative methods of analysis to investigate the extent to which lecturers' qualification could predict an effective teaching of science courses using faculty of science Federal University Gusau as a case study. In the present study, the result of data analysis gathered from the lecturers of faculty of science at Federal University Gusau, was reported.

during their teaching in their respective lecture halls and laboratories. The checklist consisted of 33 items using the four likert scale: 1= strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3=agree, and 4=strongly agree. The summary of the quantitative result is depicted in Table 1.

Table 1: Predicting influence of Lecturers Qualification on Effective Teaching of Science Courses in F U G in terms of Presentation and Pedagogy

Presentation and Pedagogy	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
G A-L1	23	36.5	1.8295
S L-Professor	40	63.5	2.1136
Total	63	100	

Table 1 shows that lecturers qualifications ranging from senior Lecturers to professors has stronger predicting influence in terms of presentation and pedagogy with (F=40, M=2.1136 and P=16.6). This indicated that forty out of sixty-three lecturers are on the rank of S.L (Senior Lecturers) and the professors who were represented by 66.6% with mean score of 2.1136. On the other hand, the lectures

qualification ranging from G.A (Graduate Assistant) to L.1 (Lecturer one) has weak or small predicting influence in terms of presentation and pedagogy with (F=23, M=1.8295 and P=36.5). This indicated that twenty-three out of sixty-three lecturers are on the rank of graduate assistant to lecturer one who were represented by 36.5% with mean score of 1.8295.

Research Question 2

To what extents would the lecturers' qualifications predict effective teaching of science courses in terms of classroom management and control in FUG?

This section discusses the predicting influence of lecturer's qualification on effective teaching of science courses in faculty of science in terms of classroom management and control. To find out this predicting influence, a checklist observation of science teaching was used and conducted with the

lecturers during their teaching in their respective lecture halls and laboratories. The checklist consisted of 33 items using the four likert scale: 1= strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3=agree, and 4=strongly agree. The summary of the quantitative result is depicted in Table 2.

Table 2: Predicting influence of Lecturers Qualification on Effective Teaching of Science Courses in F U G in terms of Classroom Management and Control

Classroom		Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Management and Control	G A-L1	26	41.3	1.1234
	S L-Professor	37	58.7	1.6116
	Total	63	100	

Table 2 shows that lecturers qualifications ranging from senior lecturers to professors has stronger predicting influence in terms of classroom management and control with (F=37 M=1.6116 and P=58.7). This indicated that thirty-seven out of sixty-three lecturers are on the rank of S.L (Senior Lecturers) and the professors who were represented by 58.7% with mean score of 1.6116. On the other hand,

the Lectures qualification ranging from G.A (Graduate Assistant) to L.1 (Lecturer one) has weak or small predicting influence in terms of classroom management and control with (F=26, M=1.11234 and P=41.3). This indicated that four out of eight Lecturers are on the rank of Graduate Assistant to Lecturer one who were represented by 41.3% with mean score of 1.1234.

Hypothesis Testing

Lecturers' qualifications is not a predictor of effective teaching of science courses in Federal University Gusau.

Table 3: Predicting influence of Lecturers Qualification on Effective Teaching of Science Courses in the Faculty of Science in F U G

Variable		R ² Excluded	F ²	Degree of effect
Presentation and Pedagogy Classroom Management and Control	GA-L1	.441	.170	Large Effect
	SL-Professor	.430	.083	Small Effect

This study adopts the criteria proposed by Cohen et al. (2013), to evaluate whether a particular independent variable has effects on the dependent variable; that is, $f^2 = .170$ as having a large effect and $f^2 = 0.083$ as having a small effect. Therefore, Table 3 shows that among the Qualifications of GA-L1 and SL-Professor, S L-Professor's qualifications have strong or large effect ($f^2 = 0.170$), and G A-L have small or weak effect on Teaching Sciences Courses in

the Faculty of Science. The analysis of this table indicated that lecturers' qualification is the predictor of effective teaching of science courses in FUG. The hypothesis is therefore rejected.

To determine which of the two Lecturers' Qualifications (G A-L1 and S L-Professor) would predict the Effective Teaching of Science Courses in FUG, a multiple regression analysis was employed and result is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Summary of multiple Regression Analysis showing Predicting influence of Lecturers' Qualifications on Effective Teaching of Science Courses in FUG

	Un-standardized co-efficient	Standard coefficient			
Model	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)	t	Sig
(constant)	37.969	3.847		9.871	.000
S L-Professor	.602	.163	.192	5.756	.000*
G A-L1	.456	.093	.169	4.923	.000*

* Significant at 0.05 Level

Based on Table 4, it is discovered that both categories of lecturers G A-L1 ($\beta = 0.16$; $t = 4.923$; $p < 0.05$) and S L-Professor ($\beta = 0.192$; $t = 5.756$; $P < 0.05$) would predict Effective Teaching of Science Courses in Federal University Gusau.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study indicated that, lecturer's qualifications' ranging from senior Lecturers to professors has stronger effects in terms of presentation and pedagogy. It is discovered that both categories of lecturers G A-L1 ($\beta = 0.16$; $t = 4.923$; $p < 0.05$) and S L-Professor ($\beta = 0.192$; $t = 5.756$; $P < 0.05$) would predict Effective Teaching of Science Courses in FUG. The study corroborates the study conducted by Aaronson (2007), where different categories of teacher variables were analyzed. Some studies focus on the impact of a teacher's gender and race on teacher quality (Dee, 2007) Tried to studied, the relationship between student outcomes and teacher qualifications such as teaching certificates or teaching experiences, Kane (2008) Observed teacher characteristics are, however, generally found to have only little impact on student achievement and can only explain a relatively small part of overall teacher quality (Rivkin et al., 2005). On the other hand, the lectures qualification ranging from G.A (Graduate Assistant) to L.1 (Lecturer one) has weak or small effects in terms of presentation and pedagogy. The result shows that lecturer's qualifications' ranging from senior lecturers to professors has stronger effects in terms of classroom management and control. On the other hand, the Lectures qualification ranging from G.A (Graduate Assistant) to L.1 (Lecturer one) has weak or small effects in terms of classroom management and control. The result of the research findings also revealed that, lecturers in the faculty of science predominantly applied lecture methods in the teaching of science courses in the lecture hall or laboratory which is in agreement with the findings of Sajjad (2010) who found that, students rated lecture method as the best teaching method, the Findings on this research indicated that most of the students rated lecture method as the best teaching method. Reasons

included; teacher provides all knowledge related to the topic, it is a time saving method; Students listen to lecture attentively and take notes. It is also in line with Hake (1998), Olatoye and Adekoya (2010) and Agpoghol (2016) who reported that, lecture methods has significant effect on teaching agriculture on female gender compared to project based methods and demonstration methods in teaching. Also the findings agree with Akinsola and Igwe (1999) who reported that the combination of the lecture teaching technique with other approaches may improve the understanding and application of Chemistry concepts

Also, this finding contradicted or disagreed with the work of Wilden (2002), Elord (2008) and Aliyu (2015) who reported in their studies that, compares teaching style (lecture method versus inquiry method) in an introductory undergraduate Biology class for non-science majors. The inquiry methods were rated for teaching Biology. Also in the report by Timmerman (2008), Malacinski (2003), the paper presented no research showing that this developmental Biology class was more effective than the traditional lecture-based developmental biology class. Also the findings of this research disagree with the work of Savinien (2002) who reported that traditional lecture method styles of teaching are doing little to improve the conceptual learning in Physics. Also findings on this research contradict the work of Babarinde (2009) who reported that Students avoid answering questions from these areas or perform poorly if attempted at-all during internal/external WAEC and NECO examinations, the result revealed that teachers need to actively engage students in teaching-learning process; hence teachers should employ students-centered teaching strategies to overcome this difficulty. Also the findings disagree with Akpoghol, (2013) who indicated that, Learning through some methods of teaching like lecture methods is passive rather than active laboratory, recitation methods) do not tend to foster critical and creative thinking, and collaborative problem-solving. It may need to be pointed that no one method of teaching chemistry is ideal all the time. Mohammad (2011) and Elvis (2013) also contradicted the results

of this study. In their studies, the researchers demonstrated that, teacher-student interactive method was the most effective teaching method, and followed by student-centred method while the teacher-centred approach was the least effective teaching method.

The work of Well and David (1995) corroborate the findings of this study where Laboratory activities were not used as much as in the cooperative inquiry or in the modelling method and were designed to reinforce concepts from class and to develop lab skills among students. More so another finding that agreed with this is study are the work of Aaronson, (2007) and Dee (2007) who reported in their work about the impact of teacher's gender and race on teacher quality. The result indicated that, male teachers with high qualification teach science subjects effectively than female teacher.

Conclusion

The study concludes that although, lecturers' qualifications are good predictors of effective teaching of science courses in Federal University Gusau, Senior Lecturer – Professorial cadre is a better predictor than GA – L1 category. Lecturers' qualification has significant effects on presentation and pedagogy of teaching science content in their lecture hall where senior Lecturers and professors performed better than the Graduate Assistant and lecturer one in their respective lecture hall. It also indicated that the senior lecturers and professors performed better in dealing with their classroom management and control in their lecture hall than the lecturer one and the Graduate assistant.

Recommendations

1. The University Management should provide opportunities for training and development of Lecturers through post graduate programme, conferences and post Graduate Diploma in education for them to understand the concept of pedagogy and classroom management and control.
2. The University Management should provide the Faculty of Science with adequate laboratory equipment, internet connectivity, adequate power supply and space expansion of laboratory buildings in each Departments. This is in order to accommodate students in carrying out their practical experiment efficiently.
3. Students in Faculty of Science should be exposed to variety of teaching methods that are activity based method that require them to involve in scientific investigation and discovery of scientific fact. That will enable them to make an impact in

the societal development in the areas of science and technology after graduation.

References

- Aaronson D, Barrow L, Sander W (2007). Teachers and Student Achievement in the Chicago Public High Schools. *J. Labor Econ.* 25(1):95-135
- Adeogun AA (2001). The principal and the financial management of public secondary schools in Osun State. *J. Educ. Syst. Dev.* 5(1):1 – 10
- Akinsolu, A. O. (2010). Teachers and students' academic performance in Nigerian secondary schools: Implication for planning. *Florida Journal of Educational Administration & policy* 3(2) pp 86 – 103
- Akpoghol T.V (2016) Effects of Lecture Method Supplemented with Music and Computer Animation on Senior Secondary School. Student. Academic Achievement in Electrochemistry: *Journal of Education and Practice (Makurdi)*.7.(2)22-35.
- Babarinde K. (2009) Strategies for Effective Knowledge Transfer: In Popoola. L Adetimirin O & Olurunnisde O (eds) *Planning and Writing Grant Oriented Proposals Proceeding of a Training of Trainers Workshop*. University of Ibadan, Ibadan.
- Dee T. (2007). Teacher Gender Gaps in Student Achievement: *The Journal of Human Resources* 42(3).528-554
- Eboutou MR, Masanja V, Mulemwa JN, Quaisie G (1998). Country Profile Reports in Female Education in Mathematics and Science in Africa, (FEMSA) of Cameroon, Tanzania, Uganda and Ghana respectively.
- Elord S. (2008) Genetics Concept Inventory: Paper Presented and Conceptual *Assessment in Biology Conference* 11.3-8 January. Asilomar California
- Elvis. M.G (2013) Teaching Method and Student Academic Performance: *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Volume. 2*
- Ewe'r(2001). Teacher – Directed versus learning cycle methods: effects on Science process skills mastery and teacher efficacy among Elementary education students: *Dissertation Abstracts International* (62(07)237A (UMI. No A. AT3022333).
- Goffman E. (1959) The presentation of self in everyday life, New York Doubleday.
- Haambokoma C, Nkhata B, Kosstyuk VS, Chabalengula V, Mbewe S, Tabakamulamu M, Ndhlovu ZB, Mushanga R, Ntan D (2002). Strengthening of mathematics and science Education in Zambian Secondary Schools. A Baseline study report, Jica/MOE, Lusaka. 2008.

- Hake R.R (1998) Interactive- Engagement versus Traditional method: A six thousand – Student Survey of machine test data for Introductory Physic Course: *American Journal of Physic.* 66(1).64.74
- Harris DN, Sass TR (2008). Teacher Training, Teacher Quality and Student Achievement.” CALDER Working Paper 3. Washington, D.C.: The Urban Institute.
- Huang, F. L. and Moon, T. R. (2009). Is experience the best teacher? A multilevel analysis of teacher characteristics and student achievement in low performing schools *Educ Asse Eval Acc* 21 pp 209 – 234
- Igwe, D. O. (1990). Science teacher qualification and students performance in secondary schools in Kano state. *Journal of Science Teacher Association o f Nigeria*, 26(2) pp24 – 51.
- Israel, Glenn D. (1992) Sampling the Evidence of Extension Program Impact Program Evaluation and Organizational Development IFAS, University of Florida. PEOD-5 October.
- Kane at el (2008).what does certification tell us about teacher effectiveness? Evidence from New York City. *Economicss of Education Review* 27 (6):615.631
- Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement.*
- Malacinski G.M (2003) Student-Oriented Learning: An Inquiry-Based Development Biology Lecture Course. *Int. S. Dev. Biol.* 47: pp.
- Mbugua ZK, Kibet K, Muthaa GM, Reche GN (2012). „Factors contributing to student” performance in mathematics at Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education: a case of Baringo County, Kenya”, *Am. J. Contemp. Res.* 2(6):87–91.
- Mohammad N. (2011): An Experimental Study on the Effectiveness of Problem-based versus Lecture – based Instructional Strategy on Achievement, Retention and Problem-solving Capabilities in Secondary School General Science Students. *:Pakistan Research Respiratory E. Prints School of Electrical and the Computer Science University of Southampton.*
- Olatoye R.A. & Adekoya Y.M (2010) Effect of Project Based, Demonstration and Lecture Teaching Strategies on Senior Secondary Students Achievement in an Aspect of Agriculture. *International Journal of Educational Research and Technology vol. (1)* Society, of Education India.
- Rivkin at et (2005) Teacher, School and Academic: achievement *Econometrica*: 73 (2):4170458.
- Sajjad .S (2010) Effective Teaching Method at Higher Level: University of Karachi Pakistan.
- Savinainen.A& Scoot, P. (2002) The Force Concept Inventory: *a tool for Monitoring Student Learning.* *PhysEdu* 37(1) 45-52
- Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2010). Research methods for business - A skill building approach. (5th, Ed.) United Kingdom: John Wiley & Sons Ltd.
- Timmerman B.E Strickland. D.C & Carstensen S.M (2008) Curricular Reform an Inquiry in Biology: Where are our Effort most fruitfully Invested? *Integrated and Comparative Biology* 48.226-240
- Well & David Hestenes (1995). A Modeling Method for High School Physic Instructor: *American Journal of Physic*: 63:606-169
- Wilden J. Crowther D. Gubanich. A. Cannon J. (2002): A Quantitative Comparison of Instruction Format of Undergraduate Introductory Level Content Biology Courses. Traditional Lecture Approach Vs Inquiry-Based Education Majors: *paper presented at the annual International Conference of the Association of Education Teacher in Science*, Charlotte North Carolin

